

TIMSS and the World Bank: Mathematics education for human capital and consumerism

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In this paper I sustain the mathematics education community's decades-long critique of international competitive assessments with my historical-contextual analysis of the IEA's TIMSS. Using perspectives on the globalization of education, I highlight TIMSS' association with the World Bank to display the assessment's motivation: increasing the people throughout the world who enter the global economy as both wage laborers and lifelong consumers. In assembling and discussing economic data, it appears that those countries participating in TIMSS do in fact increase their participation in the global economy. Such motivations and achievements should give the mathematical academic community pause as we consider engagement with TIMSS and similar globalizing efforts in mathematics education.

Introduction

Our community knows all too well the international competitive assessments in mathematics education, including the International Association for the Evaluation of Educational Achievement's (IEA) Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS) and the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development's (OECD) Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). Cogent critiques among our community of mathematics educators began as early as 40 years ago with, e.g., Freudenthal (1975). He emphasized many points including IEA's lack of engagement with mathematicians and mathematics educators and the dubious conclusions often made from the data. The present project aims to take up these conversations of critiquing TIMSS yet again and specifically by associating the project to its broader policy objectives and especially via entanglement with the World Bank.

The specifics to the critique I present here, as an historical-contextual approach, relate to other critiques of the globalization of mathematics education put forth in the community, e.g., Ernest (2009). He frames his discussion on globalization and mathematics education with the dominating discourse of the knowledge economy (an ideology central to the World Bank's activities). He suggests an "export" of Eurocentric models of education and higher education across the globe and, specific to my focus, a suggested "appropriation effect" via the international competitive assessments, as in:

Please cite as: Wolfmeyer, M. (2021). TIMSS and the World Bank: Mathematics education for human capital and consumerism. In D. Kolloosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 3, pp. 1063–1071). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5416940>

[Projects] can also be focused on applying some predetermined framework as in international assessment and comparative studies (e.g., SIMS, TIMSS, PISA) typical of scientific paradigm research. In both of these types of research there is what I shall term the *appropriation effect*. In this, locally gathered knowledge from ‘developing’ countries is appropriated for academic and other uses in ‘developed’ countries. (pp. 4–5)

In his critique, the outcomes of these assessments are suggested to have significant impact in altering the mathematics curricula throughout the globe. In my critique, I will suggest that outcomes from TIMSS and the like exactly service the broader vision of society that its associates (the World Bank and, more generally, the globe’s power-elite) desire. Namely, TIMSS activity is associated with increasing the people across the world who have entered the global economy as wage laborers and lifelong consumers.

This research presentation contains a focused argument on TIMSS using a historical-contextual method of analysis. This is one component to a broader research project in which I engage discussion of the impact of these international competitions. I refer to the phenomena as “assessment spread” and use both contextual-historical methods as well as content analysis of released assessment items for TIMSS, PISA, and (forthcoming) other activities in the globalization of mathematics education. The presentation herein offers one slice of my present work, namely the historical-contextual analysis of the IEA’s TIMSS.

Globalization and education

Regarding globalization of education, Spring (2014) offers three theoretical frameworks for interpreting the global rise of mass schooling: world culture, world systems/post colonialist and culturalist. The international competitive assessments reflect world culture theory more heavily than it does the others. World culture theory insists “all cultures are slowly integrating into a single global culture” (p. 7) yet begs the question: what are the prominent assumptions and ideologies within said monoculture? By invoking world culture theory with critical engagement, I turn the theory on its head in suggesting that the key ideologies present are a global monoculture that embraces capitalism and, specifically, viewing people as wage laborers who are also lifelong consumers. In this way I am using world culture theory differently than others: some world culture theorists suggest an evolutionary process whereby cultural practices (mostly Eurocentric) dominate because they are uncritically perceived to be better (Spring, 2014). I flip the theory by viewing the emergent monoculture through a critical lens focused on the possibility that the culture’s survival requires such dominance. In other words, the ideology of consumerism and human capital theory must spread for participants in its cultural practices to remain as such. As evidence of this requirement, take middle class US citizens as deeply committed practitioners of the consumerist culture. They need cheaper electronics in the hopes that these will deliver happiness (axiomatic to the consumerist ideology). The cheaper goods require additional peoples of the world to enter the culture of human capital, as factory workers making personal computers and cellular phones, for example.

Critical scholars of mathematics education have clearly documented the human capital embedded within mathematics education. My own work (Wolfmeyer, 2014) analyzes the social network of US national math education to reveal a consistent human capital theme amongst the individuals and organizations responsible for math education policy. Gutstein (2006) highlights where this exists in the US National Council of Teachers of Mathematics (NCTM) 1989 content standards: the four “societal goals” of math education, include economic growth and the development of human capital.

Today, economic survival and growth are dependent on new factories established to produce complex products and services with very short market cycles...Traditional notions of basic mathematical competence have been outstripped by ever-higher expectations of the skills and knowledge of workers; new methods of production demand a technologically competent workforce... Businesses no longer seek workers with strong backs, clever hands, and “shopkeeper” arithmetic skills (NCTM, 1989, pp. 3-4).

NCTM reinforces their commitment to human capital theory by suggesting mathematical literacy for all is an “economic necessity” rather than, say, a requirement for a participatory democracy. I argue that NCTM’s commitment to human capital theory and market economies, as seen here, also implies a commitment to the consumerist ideology.

These suggestions to associate dominant mathematics education practices with both human capital and consumerism is made stronger by analysing the globalization of mathematics education via the IEA’s TIMSS. As revealed in the next section, TIMSS association to the World Bank and my historical-contextual approach reveals the assessment’s engagement with furthering participation in the global economy. The data will reveal that TIMSS participating countries also increased their income levels per capita during their period of involvement. I am very careful not to suggest that TIMSS participation *caused* this circumstance; however, it certainly associates to it.

From 10 to 60+, plus the World Bank

What began as the participation of 10 wealthy nations (all from Europe except the US and Israel) now includes participating countries from Africa, Asia, Central America, South America, Asia, Oceania, Europe, and North America. The participating countries in TIMSS also now include economic diversity, with several countries having lower income categories. In the span of time since its pilot study in 1959 to the most recent iteration in 2019, the IEA’s mathematics assessment has also included perhaps its most significant player: the World Bank. Since the 1999 iteration, the World Bank has been listed as a primary funder for the project.

As a primary context for TIMSS, the World Bank and its involvement in education deserves our community’s careful attention. Looking first at their own documents on education, we see their motivations laid bare. The World Bank and their networked actors put forth the suggestion of a knowledge economy as the key for emerging economies in so-called “developing nations.” This appears in multiple World Bank publications, as in *Building knowledge economies: Advanced strategies for development* (World Bank, 2007). Similar

arguments are put forth by other organizations, such as the global economic elite (as represented by the OECD) who declare an education for human capital among the wealthy nations as the primary educational imperative, as in Keeley (2007).

Existing literature on the globalization of education provides sustained critique of the World Bank's involvement in education. Spring (2004) offers poignant analysis to the framing in which the World Bank takes educational action:

[Their] educational ideology contains a particular vision about how society should be organized. For many people, this vision is just assumed to be a necessary part of the advancement of world societies. It is an image of the good society that is often unquestioned because of its promise of economic abundance for all [...]. *As envisioned by the World Bank, a good society is one based on the mass production of consumer goods within a global economy.* Each region or nation contributes to mass production through factory and agricultural goods. The production of agricultural goods is done on large corporate farms or plantations. Small family agricultural units are replaced by large units with factory-like organization. Workers in these larger units are trained for specialized roles and work in corporate teams. Those who previously worked on family farms either work on corporate agricultural units or move to urban centers. The migration of the population from rural to urban centers follows the pattern that occurred in Western industrialized nations in the 19th and early 20th centuries. Displaced rural workers provide the labor supply for new industrial concerns. In addition, gender equality and low fertility rates free women from the home to increase the supply of labor [...]. What is valued is constant economic growth, which requires a continuous development of new products and increased consumption. There is no definable end to this process. When does a society reach a point when it does not need economic growth? Is there a point of stasis? Or is it an endless cycle of developing new products and creating consumer demand? *Of course, from the viewpoint of the World Bank, the problem is that many countries have not reached a high enough level of economic development to participate in the mass consumer society. The role of education is to help them make this leap* (pp. 40-41, emphasis added).

As Spring continues, he provides examples of the types of educational activities that the World Bank has enacted over time. These include a variety of curriculum, funding and loans, and assessment programs. In this presentation I am pointing to specifically one of these, namely the World Bank's funding of and entanglement with TIMSS. It's clear that TIMSS has been enacting the World Bank's educational ideology since at least 1999 when they acknowledged World Bank as a significant funding source.

I next merge this contextual understanding, that TIMSS engages with the World Bank's education and global society vision, with a historical approach to the participating countries in TIMSS. I compiled lists of the participating countries over time and cross-checked these with World Bank historical data on Gross National Income (GNI) per capita. They indicate the countries over time that have been brought into IEA's assessment practice in mathematics assessment. After the pilot study in 1959, we have the FIMS (First International Mathematics Study) of 1964, the SIMS (second) of 1980-1982, the TIMSS (third and to now including science) of 1995, and finally, the renaming of the practice to TIMSS (Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study) and its iteration via a 4 year cycle every year

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with the last one completed in 2019. Table 1 below includes the countries participating in the four-year iterative assessment between 1995 and 2007 but an additional variable presented: the World Bank's analytical classification for each country based on the Gross National Income per capita.

1995	1999	2003	2007
Argentina+++	Australia++++	Argentina+++	Algeria++
Australia++++	Belgium++++	Armenia++	Armenia++
Austria++++	Bulgaria++	Australia++++	Australia++++
Belgium++++	Canada++++	Bahrain++++	Austria++++
Bulgaria++	Chile+++	Belgium++++	Bahrain++++
Canada++++	Chinese Taipei++++	Botswana+++	Bosnia and
Colombia++	Cyprus++++	Bulgaria++	Herzegovina++
Cyprus++++	Czech Republic+++	Canada++++	Botswana+++
Czech Republic+++	England++++	Chile+++	Bulgaria+++
Denmark++++	Finland++++	Chinese Taipei++++	Canada++++
England++++	Hong Kong SAR++++	Cyprus++++	Chinese Taipei++++
France++++	Hungary +++	Egypt++	Colombia++
Germany++++	Indonesia+	England++++	Cyprus++++
Greece+++	Iran++	Estonia+++	Czech Republic++++
Hong Kong++++	Israel++++	Ghana+	Denmark++++
Hungary+++	Italy++++	Hong Kong SAR++++	Egypt++
Iceland+++	Japan++++	Hungary +++	El Salvador++
Indonesia++	Jordan+++	Indonesia++	England++++
Iran++	Korea++	Iran++	Georgia++
Ireland++++	Latvia++	Israel++++	Germany++++
Israel++++	Lithuania++	Italy ++++	Ghana+
Italy++++	Macedonia++	Japan++++	Hong Kong SAR++++
Japan++++	Malaysia+++	Jordan++	Hungary ++++
Korea++++	Moldova+	Korea++++	Indonesia++
Kuwait++++	Morocco++	Latvia+++	Iran++
Latvia++	Netherlands++++	Lebanon+++	Israel++++
Lithuania++	New Zealand++++	Lithuania+++	Italy ++++
Mexico+++	Philippines++	Macedonia++	Japan++++
Netherlands++++	Romania++	Malaysia+++	Jordan++
New Zealand++++	Russian Federation++	Moldova+	Kazakhstan+++
Norway++++	Singapore++++	Morocco+	Korea++++
Philippines++	Slovak Republic+++	Netherlands++++	Kuwait++++
Portugal++++	Slovenia++++	New Zealand++++	Latvia+++
Romania++	South Africa+++	Norway++++	Lebanon+++
Russian	Thailand++	Palestinian National	Lithuania+++
Federation++	Tunisia++	Authority*	Malaysia+++
Scotland++++	Turkey++	Philippines++	Malta++++
Singapore++++	USA++++	Romania++	Mongolia++
Slovak Republic++		Russian Federation++	Morocco++

1995	1999	2003	2007
Slovenia+++		Saudia Arabia+++	Netherlands++++
South Africa+++		Scotland++++	New Zealand++++
Spain++++		Serbia*	Norway++++
Sweden++++		Singapore++++	Oman++++
Switzerland++++		Slovak Republic+++	Palestinian National Authority*
Thailand++		Slovenia++++	Qatar++++
USA++++		South Africa++	Romania+++
		Spain++++	Russian Federation+++
		Sweden++++	Saudi Arabia++++
		Syria++	Scotland++++
		Tunisia++	Serbia+++
		USA++++	Singapore++++
		Yemen+	Slovak Republic++++
			Slovenia++++
			Spain++++
			Sweden++++
			Syria++
			Thailand++
			Tunisia++
			Turkey+++
			Ukraine++
			United Arab Emirates++++
			USA++++
			Yemen+

Table 1. Countries participating in TIMSS and World Bank's analytical classification for each country

I use the economic classification to make arguments about the significance of the assessment spread after displaying the tables of participating countries. In this table and a second table (not included here due to space limitations but displaying the countries that participated 2011 through 2019), the categories of economic classification include High Income, Upper middle income, Lower middle income, and Low income are displayed as +, +++, ++, and +, respectively. Thresholds for these categories vary slightly from year to year and increase over time due to inflation of the US dollar. The thresholds for 2019's analytical classifications were: Low income as GNI per capita less than \$1035 US, Lower middle between \$1036 and \$4045 US, Upper middle income between \$4046 and \$12535 US, and High income above \$12535. Sources to create these tables include the IEA (n.d.) website with lists of participating countries and World Bank Group (n.d.), a data set with historical classifications according to the economic groups listed above.

The tables reveal several interesting phenomena after careful consideration of the years and involvement over time. The simple and clear statement that this assessment has spread

across the globe throughout the years cannot be underestimated. What began as an initial pilot study to compare a handful of countries is now a consistent practice with about 61 countries participating on average in the last four iterations. And increasingly the participating countries include more diversity with respect to income categorization. It is the latter point that deserves further explication of meaning as it relates significantly to the World Bank's vision for education and global society.

Looking at the diversity of GNI per capita among the countries in the 1995 TIMSS, we see a majority of participating countries with high levels of income yet also seven that are upper middle and 11 that are lower middle income. In the next few iterations of TIMSS, the numbers of lower middle income increases (to 13 participating countries in years 1999 and 2003) and the participating countries include those with lower income now as well (two countries in 1999 and 4 in 2003). The pattern of increasing economic diversity holds steady as the cycles move on, but interestingly toward the later years we begin to see fewer numbers in the lower and lower middle income categories. In the last few years, the spread of countries has not continued to amass new participating countries similar to the rate of spread we saw earlier in time. However, here is the striking fact presented in this data: taking together the full list of participating countries in TIMSS cycles, we have 84 in total, many of these were countries with high income classifications yet some were not. *Exactly 25 countries from among all participating increased their GNI per capita income category as classified by the World Bank during the years of participation in TIMSS.* Only two of these (South Korea and South Africa) went down in classification and came back up during the years of TIMSS. The remaining 23 entered the TIMSS process in a lower income category and improved during the years they were participating in TIMSS, many holding steady at their higher income levels in the last few cycles of TIMSS. Of those countries that entered in less than "high income" and *did not* increase their incomes (18 countries total), 10 of these were one-time participants in TIMSS and don't have sustained participation in TIMSS to associate to income levels. Thus, the 23 participating countries increasing income levels more than outweighs the 8 countries that did not. As another way of looking at this data, of the 84 participating countries exactly 6 began participation as classified "low income" with exactly 5 of these increasing their income category during the years of TIMSS participation.

The increase in income level corresponds exactly to Spring's description of the World Bank's global vision. A country that increases its per capita income levels over time means that more people in the country are entering the wage labor market and have the ability to consume goods and services in market economies. When the World Bank looks at data for countries like these, it sees its vision realized: more people entering the global marketplace as both the human capital that markets need and the consumers in an ever-increasing demand for products.

Looking specifically at the TIMSS participating countries, we see an increase in GNI per capita for these 21 countries equating to *25% of all participating countries in TIMSS.* Furthermore, the majority of high-income countries hold steady at the high income level. This is remarkable data, the World Bank is surely pleased to see that countries participating

in its activities are increasing the numbers of people entering the wage labor market and increasing demands for global consumption. The World Bank and IEA might even make a leap in suggesting that the TIMSS mathematics assessment causes new mathematics education practices that in turn enable a country's citizens to enter the global economy more readily. However, such an assertion is poor mathematics. In other words, I am not pointing to any cause-and-effect relationship between TIMSS participation and the increase in income levels of participating countries; I am pointing to the association between the two. A nation-state's choice to participate is likely indicative of several other actions they are taking, many of them additionally with support of the World Bank, to increase their engagement with the global economy. At the very least, participating in TIMSS represents a country's willingness to engage in the ideology that Spring describes and it should come as no surprise, then, that the majority of countries who could increase their income levels actually did. Although there can be no suggestion of cause and effect between TIMSS and increasing global economic activity, it will serve useful to indicate further how the two are associated. This appears with additional components in my broader research project on mathematics education assessment spread across the globe, specifically the accompanying content analysis of TIMSS released items.

Discussion

In presenting this slice of my analysis of the global assessment spread of mathematics education, I aim to reinvigorate discussion and critique of these practices. The data on GNI per income for TIMSS participating countries perfectly corresponds to the World Bank's hopes for global society. This project resonates with previous critiques of the power-elites globalization of mathematics education and is but one contribution I aim to offer. Time permitting, in the presentation I can share initial findings related to my content analysis of TIMSS. Using Harouni (2015) as a framework, coding released items from TIMSS presents further research that confirm the entanglement of TIMSS with World Bank's vision. Namely, the content analysis of TIMSS reveals that the overwhelming usage of mathematics portrayed by the TIMSS practice is only of one type: commercial-administrative. By asserting the commitments and underlying assumptions in global mathematics education assessment spread, I hope that the community can continue to reject these assumptions assertively and with confidence in argumentation. Presenting these critiques also aims to motivate alternative discussions on the possibilities in globalizing mathematics differently, e.g., Appelbaum & Gerofsky (2013) pathways toward alterglobalizing mathematics education.

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